

UNDERSTANDING THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING MIX PRACTICES AND BUSINESS PERFORMANCE IN THE IT SECTORS

Author

Feng Jiaxin
SEGi University Malaysia
E-mail: 603952837@qq.com

Abstract

Purpose – The present study aims to examine how business-to-business (B2B) marketers can influence content creation in social media. Social media tools are becoming an interesting component of B2B marketing because of the roles of personal relationships and interactions in these markets. However, research has not approached social media content creation from a B2B marketing perspective.

Design/methodology/approach – Social media tools are becoming an interesting component of B2B marketing because of the roles of personal relationships and interactions in these markets. However, research has not approached social media content creation from a B2B marketing perspective. The present study examines how B2B marketers can influence content creation in social media.

Findings – The paper proposes that B2B firms engaging in social media as part of their marketing efforts should carefully consider the roles and activities of various users, which are directed to and by different internal and external users. B2B companies can influence content creation in social media directly by adding new content, participating in discussions and removing content through corporate user accounts and controlling employee social media behavior or indirectly by training employees to create desired content and performing marketing activities that influence other users to create content that is favorable for the company.

Originality/value – The study contributes to the theoretical discussion over B2B marketing communication and the role of social media in it.

Keywords: *social media, Business Performance, Social Media Marketing Mix, IT Sectors*

Background

Internet is one of the successful technologies that connecting many people in the world and changed the way of people live (Shaghghi & Antonakopoulos, 2012). In Malaysia, the number of internet population exceeds 12 million people in year 2014 (Nunan, Sibai, Schivinski, & Christodoulides, 2018). The increasing world internet population provides a huge market entity to business. Internet websites are valuable to business because it is global reach and ubiquitous without the limitation of geographical location and cost. Therefore, many companies realize the opportunities of internet and transform or expand their businesses from

traditional physical stores to online stores in order to provide products and services or serving their customer through electronic system (Mariani, Ek Styven, & Nataraajan, 2021). This new way of conducting business is now called electronic commerce or E-commerce. Today, most of the company use internet as a channel to conduct business and have an official website.

Nowadays, there is a new style of E-commerce emerging and business is conducted via social media which is called social commerce (Hunt & Hellwig, 2018). Social media is a tool for sharing information among communities such as product and service information. According to (Mei &

Genet, 2022), social media is the important driver of online purchase and sale of goods and its share increased nearly 200% in E-commerce from previous year to current year. According to (Agnihotri, Dingus, Hu, & Krush, 2016), there is a high potential of social commerce in Malaysia, more than 50% of Malaysian consumers found their desired products from company advertise and marketing in Facebook. Moreover, Malaysian citizens login into and browse on social network sites 14 billion times in every month. However, there are many previous study on consumer purchase intention is still focus in the context of E-commerce environment.

There is still insufficient research specifically study on the consumer purchase intention in social media websites. In addition, it is not clear whether the finding of previous study in the context of E-commerce consistent with the consumer purchase intention in social media websites (Özcüre, Demirkaya, & Eryigit, 2011). Many factors that influence customer purchasing intentions on social media websites have not been identified in previous studies. The emergence of social commerce totally change the way of people purchase products and services and this trend causes business to rethink their operating and marketing strategy (Khamis, Ang, & Welling, 2016; Ngai, Tao, & Moon, 2015; Özcüre et al., 2011). Therefore, this research aims to identify and examine different factors that may affect consumer purchase intention through social media marketing strategies.

Social Media as a Marketing Tool

In today's technology driven world, social networking sites have become an avenue where retailers can extend their marketing campaigns to a wider range of consumers. (Montefrio, 2020) defines social media marketing as a "connection between brands and consumers, [while] offering a personal channel and currency for user centered networking and social interaction." The tools and approaches for communicating with customers have changed greatly with the emergence of social media; therefore, businesses must learn how to use social media in a way that is consistent with their business plan (Mangold and Faulds 2009). This is especially true for companies striving to gain a competitive advantage. This review examines current literature that focuses on a retailer's development and use of social media as an extension of their marketing strategy. This

phenomenon has only developed within the last decade, thus social media research has largely focused on (1) defining what it is through the explanation of new terminology and concepts that makeup its foundations, and (2) exploring the impact of a company's integration of social media on consumer behavior (Kim & Kim, 2022).

Although social media marketing is a well-researched topic, it has only been studied through experimental and theoretical research; studies never precisely describe the benefits retailers gain from this marketing tactic. In reviewing the rich plethora of multi-disciplinary literature, it is has become clear that studies are focusing on describing what social media marketing is as well as examining what factors affect consumer behavior relative to social networking (Huang, Hu, Liu, Yu, & Yu, 2016). Despite the initial progress made by researchers, development in this area of study has been limited. Research needs to expand by providing a deeper understanding of the longterm promotional gains retailers obtain from social media marketing. More formalized studies are also needed to progress beyond theorized or predicted outcomes in order to gain knowledge of real life applications. This review of literature touches upon the gaps that currently exist within social media marketing research and points out the need for future studies to explore the benefits gained by marketing on social networking sites, especially for small retailers research has determined that retailers can increase awareness of their brand by being creative when engaging customers on social media sites (Kelly & McAdam, 2022). "As more shoppers are using social media (e.g., Twitter, Facebook, MySpace, and LinkedIn) and rely on them for marketing shopping decisions, promotion through these media has become important" (Shankar et al. 2011, 32). According to (Agnihotri et al., 2016), social media sites such as Facebook are better than other advertising avenues because it stores information on all its users thus ensuring marketing reaches a retailer's specific target market. Social media sites are a great stage for retailers to create an experience and retailers can use information stored on social media sites to improve user experience with their brand.

Furthermore, (Rezende, Bansi, Alves, & Galina, 2019) research establishes that a firm can benefit from social networks to predict the likelihood of purchase intention. This can be done by taking

into account a firm's choice of network (i.e. Facebook, Instagram, Pinterest etc.) and by examining that network's data. Assessing a network's data substantially improves a company's marketing efforts because it provides the company with vital information on the network's users, which helps determine the best social media tactics for that particular site (Rezende et al., 2019). Based on this study, it can further be argued that knowing which social media sites a company's target market utilizes is another key factor in guaranteeing that online marketing will be successful.

(Singh, Crisafulli, Quamina, & Xue, 2020) stress that retailer must go beyond the advertising aspect of social networking sites and find groundbreaking ways to use them as a way to conduct conversations with consumers, instead of a one-way communication network. (Johnson, Turnbull, & Reisslein, 2022) determined that large companies are regarding social media sites as strategic tools and some businesses are even hiring employees to oversee their social media pages. "Consumers are no longer passive receivers of marketing messages; instead, they are using Facebook, MySpace, YouTube, and Twitter to voice their opinions-both positive and negative" (Stubb & Colliander, 2019). Consumers' participation with a brand on social media reinforces the need for retailers to be active participants in social networking sites and the virtual brand communities they create.

Since social media sites can be exploited for the information it provides on consumer behavior with regards to their purchasing intentions, research further suggests that businesses should incorporate social networking sites into their business model or promotional mix. A business model is a system of codependent structures, activities, and processes that serve as a firm's organizing logic and create value for customers, itself, and its partners (Eric Boyd, Keith Harrison, & McInerney, 2021). (Patel et al., 2022) recommend that social media should be regarded as an integral part of an organization's integrated marketing strategy and should not be taken lightly. As (Zhao & Bouvier, 2022) points out, almost 1 in every 13 person in the world is an active Facebook user, which points to the potential of finding a ready market for any product or service.

Social networking sites are being utilized to enhance a company's brand appeal and increase

their target market because "new technologies allow for more personal, targeted communications, as well as increased consumer participation in the creation of marketing and brand related information" (Bziker, 2021; Eric Boyd et al., 2021; Rezende et al., 2019). (Emir Hidayat, Bamahriz, Hidayati, Sari, & Dewandaru, 2021) stress that traditional communication examples, which relied on the classic promotional mix to create integrated marketing communications, must give way to a new paradigm that includes all forms of social media as potential tools in designing and implementing integrated marketing communication strategies. Retailers are paying attention when it comes to social media because it provides a key component that businesses have struggled to collect for years: feedback (Agnihotri et al., 2016). Feedback from consumers has always been important when it comes to product, brand, and business model development. Since, most studies have examined social media marketing in terms of suggesting how to incorporate it within a business plan, and how to gauge consumers' responses, it is important that further research address which strategies work. Although some studies have started to touch upon influences and factors that affect consumers' responses, previous research does not clearly state if social media marketing is valuable to retailers' in terms of return on investment.

Moreover, research based on a small retailer's perspective is limited. How have smaller firms utilized social media within their business model? How successful has social media been with increasing their customer base, brand awareness, and sales? It has become clear that when marketers from large corporations present a new product or brand, they consider both traditional and nontraditional media in which to place advertising in order to make sure they reach their target market (Mei & Genet, 2022). Small retailers also need to start utilizing nontraditional methods of marketing in creative and engaging ways to make certain that they attract a larger number of consumers. (Duffy, 2020) states "another way in which retailers can engage customers is by selling not just products, but an entire experience that - while centered on the products, adds an entirely new exciting layer to the retail setting.

Problem Statement

Until now, research has not approached social media content creation from a B2B marketing perspective. A review of the existing literature reveals that this topic has been examined mainly from the perspectives of business-to-consumer (B2C) marketing (Rezende et al., 2019) or internal corporate communications or recruiting (Kim & Kim, 2022). UGC creation involves the willingness of customers to engage in activities related to co-creation, community and self-concept (Nunan et al., 2018). Additionally, user-generated content creation has been connected to brand equity because, according to research, firm-created social media communication impacts functional brand images, whereas UGC creates hedonic brand images (Montefrio, 2020). It has been proposed that the optimization of UGC is central to applications of new interactive social media in marketing communication. The increasing adoption of new media channels in marketing communications related to brand and management of customer relationships motivates research in this area. Thus, the purpose of this study is to examine how B2B marketers can influence content creation in social media.

The major implications of the development of Internet technology for marketing communications are interactivity, transparency and memory (Huang et al., 2016). With respect to memory and transparency, companies are concerned that Internet-based information, especially negative online conversations about a company, can extend to bad publicity and reach the top of search engine results (Nunan et al., 2018). These elements enable opportunities for B2B marketers, but they also pose challenges and may cause some B2B firms to hesitate to use social media. Indeed, B2B organizations seem to have acknowledged the potential of social media more slowly than B2C companies (Dhanesh & Duthler, 2019).

(Kim & Kim, 2022) noted that creating a dialogue through interactivity is an important feature of the Internet. For B2B companies, social network sites enable interactions with their customers for creating customer value, as well as building and fostering relationships (Tuncer, 2021). According to (Kim & Kim, 2022), interactivity can be defined as the synchronous exchange of information or the way two or more organisms relate to each other. Interactivity between people may be direct or occur through a medium.

Literature Review

Social Media Marketing Strategies

Media is a great platform for people around the world to communicate and share ideas by using the internet to provide a platform to express themselves to friends and other social circles. Social Media is another form of communication that can promote products, services, and even allows customers to express recent experiences with a business. Social Media provides the much needed connection for companies to bridge a relationship with their consumers on a much personal level. This connection between business and consumer is strengthened because transparency and credibility is monitored and also reinforced. In addition, social media has become a marketing focus that can change the popularity of a brand and may boost the sales of another. Marketers are beginning to understand the use of social media as a component in their marketing strategies and campaigns to reach out to customers. Promotions, marketing intelligence, sentiment research, public relations, marketing communications, and product and customer management are sub-disciplines of marketing that may use social media. (Akar, 2011).

Social Media Marketing has become important for businesses of all sizes for the following reasons: access to information of products and services, provides ability for consumers to show loyalty or preference of products or services, gives immediate access to customer reviews of a given service or product that provides platform for social media users to share experiences and comment. Social Media has become exceedingly popular because of the amount of users that are found to be using the popular social media websites like Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter.

There are two kinds of consumers the one who is researching a product and one who is persuaded to try out a product based on customer reviews. Many consumers may express their experience of a product or a service on a specific social media website. Businesses understand that word-of-mouth is very important when people share his/her experience whether it may be a gas station or calling a utility provider for customer service. Information is more available and attainable with the internet and now has the additional access of researching on a specific product on the company's social media webpage.

Many businesses are updating their profile daily to keep up with the changes and topics to answer the most asked questions about new changes in services or products. Overall, information is the connection piece for customers to begin their preference over one product over the other.

When a customer is loyal to a specific brand, many would share and promote thru social media outlets to express reasons why they enjoy a service or product. Brand loyalty can be especially important for companies to test their presence on social media websites, popularity of the brand, and how it favors against other industry competitors. Companies test their presence of a product or service by how many users on a social media website intentionally “like” the product or service or even “tweet”. Brand loyalty can also provide the measurement of how many customers are familiar with the product or service and how many people are happy to promote to friends and family. This brand loyalty can help foster special promotions for discounts and pricing on services and products.

Another great reason for the success of social media websites in relation to businesses is the ability to monitor the firm’s standing in real time from the consumer perspective and access to specific customers if a focus group may be needed. With social media, you may find many people commenting and sharing either the same or different experience with the product. This provides an unbiased approach which gives honest feedback and does not affect the brand loyalty of other consumers.

The advantages of social media marketing of business entrepreneurs is that it gives an addition for marketing to reach out to current customers and potential clients. Social Media Marketing gives similar advantages over regular homepage websites like informing of a new change in service or product in real-time, low-cost in setting up social media profiles and allows business to generate profit and traffic to home websites for purchases and transactions, and even allows companies as mentioned earlier to reach to a bigger pool of consumers at one time. These same advantages are also inclined to some disadvantages of using social media websites. Disadvantages will include older customers who do not have access to computers and do not understand online social media attempts. Other examples of a disadvantage are consumers who

do not access to computers and not able to use social media websites to take advantage of web promotions and business marketing attempts.

Businesses that use social media websites can expect that many consumers will use the social webpage to voice grievances or praises of customer service experiences or about the actual tried product or service. Although the advantages of having a social media website to promote a specific company, it allows the business to keep up with advancements in technology and being able to reach its consumer base. On the other hand while steadily trying to improve and update marketing strategies, it is very important for these same businesses to keep up with traditional consumer base who are fine with radio, television, and newspaper advertisements. Another great advantage is that social media websites provide a link to customer’s real profile in how they use the product or service and can give honest feedback. This provides access for companies to react with suggestions and improvements that can help with boosting sales for the company. Also, providing contact for potential new customer and loyal customers helps address the company goal in establishing and continuing brand loyalty. Organizations that manage to bridge internal and external social strategies develop enterprise social maturity (Fenwick, 2012).

Social Media and Business Performance

The subject of electronic marketing has brought the researchers attention over the time (Saravanakumar and SuganthaLakshmi, 2012: Hoffman and Fodor, 2010:Neti, 2011: Constantinides, 2014: Felix et al., 2017: Alves et al., 2016). According to Schulze (2015), there is a significant increase in the number of the users of social media, the substantial increase in the use of social media has created a new potential

market in which the Hut seek to communicate with customers, social media marketing enhances a channel to reach customer worldwide, interact with them hear their voices for performance improvement (Tafesse and Wien, 2018). Furthermore, in support Lepkowska (2019) concluded that almost all of small restaurants are neither willing nor able to invest in social media, moreover some studies confirmed that many organizations are like to save money and adopt social media marketing but is not relevant to restaurant operations, social media enhance small restaurant with good chances (Assaad and Gómez 2011), and major contributions can be gained from social media platform and networks (Schaupp and Bélanger, 2013). Therefore, from the literature reviewed above, majority of the researcher conclude that social media marketing is suitable strategy for improve sales revenue performance.

Figure 1: Social media and business performance

Hypothesis Development

Social consumers are dexterous, willing to pay and participate. Their preferences are broadcast and magnified by social media, with increasing connections to corporations and brands (Berthon, Pitt, McCarthy, & Kates, 2007; Hanna, Rohm, & Crittenden, 2011; Parent, Plangger & Bal, 2011). Thus, social media has become a high corporate priority; the vast majority of traded companies are actively present on some kind of social platform. Companies are only now starting to realize the business implications and nature of this new user-generated content. Along with the challenges and opportunities that social media offers, there is a significant degree of uncertainty among managers with respect to allocating effort and budget to social media (DesAutels, 2011; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010; Weinberg & Pehlivan, 2011). As a result, practitioners often find themselves on social media quicksand, undertaking decisions without a clear understanding of the effects of social media on business performance.

Method

A qualitative method was used to collect data. Reviewing the previous researches by other researchers will provide the theory and model to address similar problems, hence, the implication and recommendation showed after the review

the previous researches, the survey distributed after the planned intervention to evaluate the process of transformation is it successful or not. 202 social media entrepreneurs were participated in this study.

Sample and procedure

Sampling is the process of selecting the sample from a population in order to obtain information regarding a phenomenon in a way that represents the population of interest (Wu Suen, Huang, & Lee, 2014). Sampling is the process by which informants are selected (Thomas et al., 2010). In quantitative research, the sampling process is of great importance, as it helps a researcher to obtain a sample that is representative of the population (Lohr & Loehr, 2019).

For this study employees of leather industry in Bangladesh are selected as a population those who are working in various organizations. Population is the collection of the elements which has some or the other characteristic in common. Number of elements in the population is the size of the population. Sample is the subset of the population. The process of selecting a sample is known as sampling. Number of elements in the sample is the sample size (Nordgaard & Correll, 2018). According to Morgan (1970), the required sample size is 384.

Findings

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Discussion

Implications

Marketing strategies have gained significant attention by scholars due to their significant impact on company performance and customer communication. (Shamim & Park, 2021), Moreover, there is almost a consensus about the importance of depending on long run marketing strategies that assist organisations in achieving their aims (Aghazadeh, 2015; Saif, 2015; Bang and Singh, 2016; Hult and Ketchen, 2017; Song et al, 2018; .Morgan et al, 2019; Mothersbaugh et al, 2019; Goncharova et al, 2019; Chou et al, 2020;

Varadarajan, 2020; Rana et al, 2020). Scholars have begun giving more attention to marketing strategies, highlight customer behaviour and its relation with marketing strategies, particularly the transition of customers to the use of social media platforms and the way that the market responds to such a shift (Patruti, 2016 ; Saura et al, 2017; Leite and Azevedo 2017; De Pelsmacker et al, 2018; Alghizzawi, 2019; Melović et al, 2020; Dwivedi et al, 2020; Finotto and Mauracher, 2020).

However, the number of studies examining the use of social media platforms and how companies have responded to the COVID-19 outbreak by activating and enhancing the company's online marketing strategies, this research provide some opportunities to understand the pandemic's implications on the adopted marketing strategies, thus contributing to the extension of existing literature related to social media usage

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